

Importance of modern pedagogical technologies

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of current modern pedagogical technologies.

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The 21st century is the age of modern computer technologies. The modern child lives in the world of electronic culture. In the information culture, the role of the teacher is also changing - he should be the coordinator of the information flow. Therefore, the teacher must have modern techniques and new pedagogical technologies to communicate with the child in the same language. The rapid development of new information technologies and their introduction in our country has left a mark on the development of a modern child's personality. Today, a new link-pedagogical technology is introduced into the traditional scheme of "teacher-student-textbook". One of the main parts of educational informatization is the use of pedagogical technologies in education. Pedagogical technology is a set of systematic methods that allow to determine the interaction of human potential and technical resources in the process of knowledge acquisition and training in order to optimize forms of education. Technology means a process that leads to a change in the quality of the subject as a result of the subject's influence on the object.

Today, practically every student has a computer at home or has permanent access to it elsewhere. Therefore, teaching school subjects with the help of a blackboard and chalk no longer inspires interest in learning them. Why is the child's interest in computers not used in the educational process? You solve all the examples correctly - open the picture, enter all the letters correctly - your favorite fairy-tale character moves forward towards his goal, etc. The use of pedagogical technologies makes it possible to combine game and educational activities will give. And not only. Many teachers with little experience in using pedagogical technologies can claim that they have the following capabilities:

- Pedagogical technologies in classes strengthen positive learning motivation, activate students' cognitive activity;

- the use of pedagogical technologies allows classes to be held at a high aesthetic and emotional level; provides visibility, involves a large amount of didactic material;
- the amount of work done in the lesson increases by 1.5-2 times; a high level of differentiation of education is ensured (almost individualization);
- the possibility of independent activity is expanding; real research activity skills are being formed;
- access to various information systems, electronic libraries and other information resources is provided; And all together, of course, helps to improve the quality of education. The following directions are often used to implement these opportunities:
 - creating slide presentations for the textbook;
 - creating flash animations for the textbook;
 - preparation of individual cards for training;
 - preparation of additional material;
 - use of ready-made electronic educational materials.

Students of grades 1-4 have visual-metaphorical thinking, therefore, involving new things in the process of perceiving new things not only by seeing, but also by hearing, emotions, imagination, using high-quality visual materials as much as possible, their training. It is very important to build the training. The most important thing in the learning process is to arouse the child's interest in learning. After all, the great Czech teacher Jan Amos Comenius created textbooks that are based on the principle of interest in learning, "because love and admiration are the most powerful means of arousing the desire to imitate." He is also the founder of the scientific approach to solving the problem of interest theoretically and practically.

The most effective means of introducing the child to the creative process in the lesson:

- game activity;
- creating positive emotional situations;
- work in pairs;
- problem education.

In primary school, it is impossible to teach without the use of visual aids, problems often arise. Where to find the right material and what is the best way to display it? The computer will help you find answers to the questions.

The most effective e-learning resources are multimedia resources. In them, learning objects are represented in many different ways: text, graphics, photos, videos, audio and animation. Thus all kinds of perception are used; therefore, a foundation is created for the child's thinking and practical activities. Multimedia resources do not replace teachers and textbooks, but at the same time create radically new opportunities for mastering the material.

In conclusion, we can conclude that the educational process is aimed at developing logical and critical thinking, imagination, and independence using pedagogical technologies. Children are interested, get acquainted with creative research; everyone's mental activity is activated. The process will be creative rather than boring and monotonous. And the emotional origin of the lesson will be more comfortable, which is very important for the educational activity of the child.

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